

Synthetic Studies on Necrodols[†]

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The synthesis of substituted cyclopentane derivatives **11** and **19** as potential intermediates for the monoterpenes necrodols has been described.

β -Necrodol **1**, a monoterpene alcohol has been isolated¹ alongwith α -necrodol **2** from the defensive spray of the red-lined carrion beetle *Necrodes surinamensis*. Unlike the other monoterpenes, the 1,2,2,3,4-pentamethylcyclopentane (necrodane) skeleton is interesting in the sense that it can not be derived from direct cyclisation of geranyl pyrophosphate. Due to the unique structural feature combined with insect repellent properties, necrodols have become attractive targets for synthesis over the years².

Results and Discussion

Recently, we have developed a general methodology for the construction of substituted cyclopentanones³ and spirocyclopentanones⁴ at the carbonyl carbon of a ketone. This methodology has recently been employed in the synthesis of capnellene⁵ and α -cedrene⁴. Using acetone as the starting ketone, this route has offered an excellent way of constructing the cyclopentanone **4**⁶ as delineated in Scheme

The synthesis of necrodols is attended with a number of challenges. The most difficult task is the establishment of the *trans*-relationship between 1,3-substituents which could never be achieved. Second, the construction of densely substituted cyclopentane framework is not a trivial job. A partial solution to this problem was offered by camphor derivatives. In the present approach to necrodols, construction of the necrodane skeleton was thus given the prime importance. Retrosynthetic analysis dictated that necrodols can be derived from the cyclopentanone **3** which in turn might be available from the cyclopentanone derivative **4**. Herein we describe results of our investigation on the synthesis of necrodols based on this retrosynthetic analysis.

1. Reaction of acetone with ethoxyvinyl lithium followed by allylation of the resulting carbinol afforded the diallyl ether **5** in excellent yield. Irradiation of an ethereal solution of the diene **5** with a medium pressure mercury vapour lamp (450 W) through a water-cooled quartz immersion well in presence of copper(I)trifluoromethane sulfonate (CuOTf) as catalyst led smooth cycloaddition to form the cyclobutane derivative **6**. Treatment of a dichloromethane solution of **6** with trifluoromethane sulfonic acid effected smooth ring enlargement of the cyclobutane ring to afford the hydroxycyclopentanone **4** in overall good yield. For introduction of the third Me group, the hydroxy group of the hydroxycyclopentanone **4** was protected as tetrahydropyranyl ether

Scheme 1. Reagents and conditions: (i) Ethyl vinyl ether, ^tBuLi, -78°, THF, 81%, (ii) NaH, HMPA, allyl bromide, THF, 73%, (iii) *hν*, CuOTf, Et₂O, 88%, (iv) TFAH, CH₂Cl₂, -78° to RT, 2 h, 84%.

[†]Dedicated to Professor Sukh Dev on the occasion of his 75th. birth anniversary.

Scheme 2. Reagents and conditions: (i) 3,4-Dihydro-2H-pyran, PPTS, CH_2Cl_2 , RT, 12 h, 95%; (ii) MeMgI , Et_2O , 0° ; (iii) PTSA, MeOH, RT, 6 h, 57%, 2 steps; (iv) DMSO, $160\text{--}65^\circ$, 3 h, 56%; (v) $\text{BH}_3\text{-THF}$, 30% H_2O_2 , 3 M NaOH, 83%; (vi) Jones reagent, acetone, 0° to RT, 1 h; (vii) CH_2N_2 , Et_2O , 58%, 2 steps.

to afford the ketone 7. Addition of MeMgI to 7 followed by removal of the protective group afforded the diol 8 as a crystalline compound, m.p. $87\text{--}89^\circ$ (Scheme 2). Examination of the ^1H nmr spectrum of the product revealed that addition of Me had taken place to form only a single diastereoisomer as indicated by the presence of only three Me singlets at δ 0.91, 0.98 and 1.19. This is further supported by ^{13}C nmr studies of the product showing three Me's at δ 17.61, 21.86 and 29.27. Anticipating that addition of nucleophile would take place from the face opposite to CH_2OH group at C_3 to avoid 1,3-eclipsing interaction, the stereochemical assignment to the addition product was made as depicted in the structure 8. Selective dehydration of the tertiary OH in the diol 8 was achieved by heating it in DMSO to afford the cyclopentene 9 as a liquid in 56% yield. The presence of an olefinic proton at δ 5.24 (m) in ^1H nmr and two olefinic carbons, one methine at δ 121.67 and a quaternary carbon at δ 148.67 in ^{13}C nmr spectra confirmed the structure of the cyclopentene as 9. Hydroboration of the cyclopentene derivative 9 followed by oxidation of the intermediate organoborane with alkaline hydrogen peroxide afforded the diol 10 as a colourless oil in 83% yield after chromatography. ^1H nmr [(300 MHz) δ 0.57 (3H, s), 0.92 (3H, d, J 6.9 Hz), 0.98 (3H, s), 1.44–1.49 (1H, m), 1.77–2.04 (2H, m), 3.37–3.81 (4H, m)] as well as ^{13}C nmr [(75 MHz) δ 10.94 (CH_3), 15.88 (CH_3), 26.76 (CH_3), 36.97 (CH_2), 41.80, 50.08 (CH), 54.15 (CH), 63.84 (OCH_2), 77.73 (OCH)] spectral data of the product indicated it to be a single diastereoisomer. We anticipated that the hydroxymethylene group would direct borane addition from its own face to establish a *trans* relationship between the Me and CH_2OH group.

That addition of the borane to the olefin 9 took place from the side opposite to the hydroxymethylene group was confirmed by Jones oxidation of the diol followed by esterification (CH_2N_2) of the resulting keto-acid to the known keto-ester 11 in which the 1,3-substituents are *syn* to each other. With the establishment of the structure of the keto-ester as 11, the stereochemistry of the diol 10 was established. This in turn proved that during hydroboration of the cyclopentene 9, addition of borane took place from the face opposite to the hydroxymethylene group.

The keto-ester 11 obtained in enantiomerically pure form from 1-bornyl acetate has been transformed to (+)-*epi*- β -necrodol and β -necrodol by Jacobs *et al.*^{2d} as follows. The keto-ester 11 was epimerised with NaOMe-MeOH to give rise to a mixture of *cis*- and *trans*-keto-esters 11 and 12 in 3 : 1 ratio. This mixture was then transformed to (+)-*epi*- β -necrodol and β -necrodol 1 through methylenation of the ketone followed by reduction of the ester functionality with lithium aluminum hydride. Thus, with the synthesis of the keto-ester 11 formal syntheses of both (\pm)-*epi*- β -necrodol and β -necrodol are accomplished.

The failure of the hydroboration of the cyclopentene derivative 9 to establish the desired 1,3-*trans* relationship between Me and CH_2OH led us to consider the following alternative path (Scheme 3). We envisaged that catalytic hydrogenation of the cyclopentene derivative 16 would lead hydrogen delivery *syn* to the CH_2OH group⁴. The resulting cyclopentane derivative 17 will then have 1,3-Me and CH_2OH *trans*-oriented. The synthesis of the cyclopentene carboxaldehyde 16 from the cyclopentanone 4 was thus undertaken following the literature procedure⁷ involving ad-

Scheme 3. Reagents and conditions: (i) $\text{CH}(\text{OMe})_3$, $^i\text{Pr}_2\text{NEt}$, $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}$, CH_2Cl_2 , 79%, (ii) MeMgI , Et_2O , 0° to RT, 70%, (iii) $n\text{Bu}_4\text{NF}$, THF, 12 h, RT, 65%.

dition of MeMgI to β -keto-acetal **14** and subsequent acid induced dehydration of the cyclopentanol **15**.

Towards this end, the hydroxy group in the cyclopentanone derivative **4** was protected to produce the *t*-butyl dimethyl silyl ether **13** in 72% yield. The cyclopentanone **13** was then transformed to the β -keto-acetal **14** in excellent yield using the reagent combination $\text{HC}(\text{OMe})_3$ - $^i\text{Pr}_2\text{NEt}$ - $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}$. The keto-acetal **14** was then allowed to react with excess of MeMgI and the resulting adduct was treated with 6*N* HCl. To our dismay the resulting product was not the desired cyclopentene carboxaldehyde **16** as revealed from spectroscopic data. For characterisation of the product, the intermediate addition product (expected to have the structure **15**) was purified through chromatography and subjected to spectroscopic analysis. ^1H nmr spectrum of this product showed the presence of three Me singlets at δ 0.88, 0.89 and 1.15 in addition to the Me's of the silyl protective group.

An additional Me group at δ 1.58 as a doublet of a triplet with the coupling constants 6.6 and 1.5 Hz and an olefinic proton at δ 5.53 were indicative of the presence of a vinylic Me and one vicinal and two allylic hydrogens, i.e. the unit $\text{CH}_2\text{C} : \text{CHMe}$. This was further corroborated from ^{13}C nmr spectrum showing one olefinic CH at δ 115.5 and an olefinic quaternary carbon at δ 148.4. Both ^1H and ^{13}C nmr spectra showed the absence of OMe groups. Based on these spectral data, the addition product was assigned the structure **18**. The structure of the product was confirmed by deprotection of the silyl group to produce the cyclopentane derivative **19**.

The formation of the product **18** from the β -keto-acetal **14** may be attributed as follows (Scheme 4). Under strongly basic condition (MeMgI in ether), the formation of the enolate **20** followed by elimination of a methoxide probably takes precedence over nucleophilic addition to the steri-

Scheme 4

cally hindered carbonyl group to produce the enone **21**. Since the carbonyl group in **21** is sterically hindered, addition of MeMgI takes place on its canonical form **22** (i.e. 1,4-addition⁸ to **21**) to produce the enolate **23**. This is followed by elimination of methoxide to produce the enone **24**. A second molecule of MeMgI then adds to the carbonyl group anti to the silyloxy methylene group at C₃ to produce **18**. The intermediacy of the enone **21** during MeMgI addition to the β -keto-acetal **14** could be proved by treating the β -keto-acetal **14** with a non-nucleophilic base, e.g. LDA to produce the enone **21** in 60% isolated yield. Reaction of the enone **21** with MeMgI also produced the same cyclopentane derivative **18**.

In conclusion, the investigation aimed at the total synthesis of necrodols has led to development of a simple stereocontrolled approach to densely substituted cyclopentanes with the formal synthesis of (\pm)- β -necrodol and *epi*- β -necrodol.

Experimental

M.ps. were taken in open capillary in sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. Column chromatography were performed on silica gel (60–120 mesh). Petroleum refers to the fraction of b.p. 60–80°. Ether refers to diethyl ether. The organic extracts were dried with anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Peak positions in ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectra are indicated in ppm downfield from internal TMS in δ units. Nmr spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ solutions at 300 MHz on Bruker DPX-300 spectrometer. Elemental analyses were performed at the microanalytical laboratory of this department.

1,2,2-Trimethyl-1 α -hydroxy-3 α -hydroxymethyl cyclopentane (8): The hydroxycyclopentanone **4** was prepared following our previously published procedure⁶. A mixture of the alcohol **4** (1.1 g, 7.74 mmol), 3,4-dihydro-2H-pyran (1.3 g, 15.49 mmol) and PPTS (0.05 g) in dichloromethane (20 ml) was stirred at room temperature under nitrogen for 12 h. After evaporation of the solvent, the crude mass was subjected to chromatography using ether-petroleum (1 : 9) as eluent to afford the tetrahydropyranyl derivative **7** (1.66 g, 95%) as a colourless thick liquid: ¹H nmr δ 0.91 (s) and 0.94 (s) (total 3H), 1.11 (3H, s), 1.54–2.37 (11H, m), 3.38–3.54 (2H, m), 3.79–3.90 (2H, m), 4.57–4.60 (1H, m). A solution of the ketone **7** (2.5 g, 11.05 mmol) in ether (20 ml) was added dropwise into a magnetically stirred MeMgI in ether [prepared from activated magnesium (1.07 g, 44.22 mmol) and MeI (7.8 g, 55.25 mmol) in ether (25 ml)] at 0° under argon. The reaction mixture was allowed to come to room temperature slowly and was stirred at that temperature overnight (12–16 h). It was cooled to 0° and quenched by dropwise addition of cold saturated NH₄Cl solution. The organic layer was separated and the

aqueous part was extracted with ether (3 \times 20 ml). The combined organic extracts were washed with brine and dried. Evaporation of the solvent left an oily residue (2.75 g). The residue was dissolved in MeOH (30 ml) and PTSA (0.05 g) was added and the mixture was stirred under nitrogen for 6 h at room temperature. Evaporation of the solvent and chromatography using ether-petroleum (7 : 3) afforded the diol **8** (1.0 g, 57%) as a white solid, m.p. 87–89° as a single diastereomer: (Found: C, 68.11; H, 11.47. C₉H₁₈O₂ calcd. for: C, 68.30; H, 11.47%); ¹H nmr δ 0.91 (3H, s), 0.98 (3H, s), 1.19 (3H, s), 1.70–1.88 (5H, m), 3.25 (1H, bs), 3.52 (1H, dd, *J* 10.8 and 2.1 Hz), 3.72 (1H, d, *J* 10.8 Hz); ¹³C nmr δ 17.61 (CH₃), 21.86 (CH₃), 22.20 (CH₂), 29.27 (CH₃), 38.42 (CH₂), 46.77, 50.24 (CH), 62.80 (OCH₂), 81.82.

1,2,2-Trimethyl-3 α -hydroxymethylcyclopent-1-ene (9): A solution of the diol **8** (0.36 g, 2.27 mmol) in DMSO (5 ml) was heated under argon for 3 h at 160–65°. It was then cooled, poured carefully into cold water (7 ml) and extracted with ether (3 \times 20 ml). The combined ether extracts were washed with water, dried and concentrated. Chromatography using ether-petroleum (1 : 9) as eluent afforded the cyclopentene **9** (0.18 g, 56%) as a light yellow thick liquid: (Found: C, 77.32; H, 11.47. C₉H₁₆O calcd. for: C, 77.08; H, 11.51%); ¹H nmr δ 0.87 (3H, s), 1.09 (3H, s), 1.60 (3H, s), 1.97–2.11 (2H, m), 2.35–2.36 (1H, m), 3.66 (1H, dd, *J* 10.5 and 7.8 Hz), 3.81 (1H, dd, *J* 10.5 and 6 Hz), 5.24 (1H, m); ¹³C nmr δ 12.62 (CH₃), 20.24 (CH₃), 27.27 (CH₃), 33.72 (CH₂), 46.83, 52.29 (CH), 64.75 (OCH₂), 121.67 (CH), 148.67.

1 α ,2,2-Trimethyl-3 α -hydroxymethyl-5 β -hydroxycyclopentane (10): Diborane gas [generated by dropwise addition of NaBH₄ (0.4 g, 10.57 mmol) in diglyme (11 ml) into a solution of BF₃·Et₂O (3.0 g, 21.13 mmol) in diglyme (5 ml)] was bubbled through a solution of the cyclopentene **9** (0.08 g, 0.54 mmol) in THF (4 ml) at 0° under a constant flow of nitrogen for 15 min. The cold reaction mixture was then quenched by adding a few drops of cold water carefully, followed by the addition of NaOH solution (2 ml; 3 *M*). To the cold mixture was then added H₂O₂ (30%; 2 ml) and left overnight. It was extracted with ether (3 \times 25 ml), the combined ether extracts washed with brine and dried. Evaporation of the solvent and chromatography using ethyl acetate as eluent afforded the diol **10** (0.07 g, 83%) as a colourless oil: (Found: C, 68.05. H, 11.41. C₉H₁₈O₂ calcd. for: C, 68.30; H, 11.47%); ¹H nmr δ 0.57 (3H, s), 0.92 (3H, d, *J* 6.9 Hz), 0.98 (3H, s), 1.44–1.49 (1H, m), 1.77–2.04 (2H, m), 3.37–3.81 (4H, m); ¹³C nmr δ 10.94 (CH₃), 15.88 (CH₃), 26.76 (CH₃), 36.97 (CH₂), 41.80, 50.08 (CH), 54.15 (CH), 63.84 (OCH₂), 77.73 (OCH).

Methyl-2 α ,3,3-trimethylcyclopent-1-one-4 α -carboxylate (**11**): Jones reagent was added dropwise to a magnetically stirred solution of the diol **10** (0.06 g, 0.38 mmol) in acetone (1 ml) at 0° till the orange colour of the reagent persisted. The mixture was allowed to stir at room temperature and monitored by tlc till the whole diol was consumed (~ 1h). The reaction mixture was diluted with ethyl acetate (10 ml) and the organic layer was washed with brine, dried and solvent evaporated to produce a residue (0.06 g). It was treated with a solution of diazomethane in ether and evaporation of the solvent and chromatography using ether-petroleum (1 : 9) as eluent afforded the keto ester **11** (0.04 g, 58%) as a colourless liquid: ¹H nmr δ 0.7 (3H, s), 0.98 (3H, d, *J* 6.9 Hz), 1.32 (3H, s), 2.06 (1H, dq, *J* 6.9 and 0.9 Hz), 2.48 (1H, ddd, *J* 19.2, 8.7 and 1.2 Hz), 2.71 (1H, dd, *J* 19.2 and 11.1 Hz), 2.88 (1H, dd, *J* 11.1 and 8.7 Hz), 3.76 (3H, s); ¹³C nmr δ 7.32 (CH₃), 17.16 (CH₃), 26.89 (CH₃), 37.95 (CH₂), 42.44, 50.24 (CH), 51.73 (CH₃), 56.60 (CH), 172.52 (CO), 216.50 (CO).

2,2-Dimethyl-3-tert-butyl dimethylsilyloxymethylcyclopentanone (**13**): A solution of the hydroxyketone **4** (1.09 g, 7.04 mmol), TBDMSCl (1.6 g, 10.6 mmol), triethylamine (2.1 g, 20.8 mmol), DMAP (0.01 g) and imidazole (0.01 g) in dichloromethane (20 ml) was stirred under nitrogen for 12 h at room temperature. The mixture was then washed with brine, dried and concentrated. The residue was chromatographed using ether-petroleum (1 : 19) as eluent to afford the silyl ether **13** (1.3 g, 72%) as a colourless liquid: ¹H nmr δ 0.01 (6H, s), 0.83 (9H, s), 0.88 (3H, s), 1.04 (3H, s), 1.51–1.58 (1H, m), 1.93–2.06 (2H, m), 2.12–2.21 (1H, m), 2.27–2.36 (1H, m), 3.57–3.67 (2H, m).

2,2-Dimethyl-5-dimethoxymethyl-3-tert-butyl dimethylsilyloxymethylcyclopentanone (**14**): A solution of freshly distilled BF₃.Et₂O (1.7 g, 12 mmol) in dichloromethane (10 ml) was added dropwise to freshly distilled trimethyl orthoformate (1.0 g, 9.5 mmol) with stirring at –30° under argon. The mixture was warmed to 0° and allowed to stand at that temperature for 15 min. It was then cooled to –78° and a solution of the silyl ether **13** (1.24 g, 4.84 mmol) in dichloromethane (5 ml) was added dropwise, followed by addition of *N,N*-diisopropylethylamine (1.85 g, 14.35 mmol). The mixture was stirred at –10° to –20° for 2 h. It was then poured into saturated NaHCO₃ solution. The organic layer was washed several times with brine, dried and concentrated. Chromatography of the residue using ether-petroleum (1 : 19) as eluent afforded the keto-acetal **14** (1.26 g, 79%) as colourless liquid: ¹H nmr δ 0.02 (6H, s), 0.83 (9H, s), 0.92 (3H, s), 1.02 (3H, s), 1.65–1.72 (1H, m), 1.99–2.05 (1H, m), 2.17–2.26 (1H, m), 2.69–2.76 (1H, m), 3.33 (3H, s), 3.34 (3H, s), 3.59 (2H, dd, *J* 6 Hz and 3

Hz), 4.51 (1H, d, *J* 3 Hz); ¹³C nmr δ –5.63 (CH₃), 18.13, 18.8 (CH₃), 23.47 (CH₂), 24.25 (CH₃), 25.85 (CH₃), 46.98 (CH), 47.95, 50.15 (CH), 55.01 (OCH₃), 56.80 (OCH₃), 64.41 (OCH₂), 105.75 (CH), 221.56 (CO).

Reaction of the keto-acetal 14 with methylmagnesium iodide: A solution of the ketone **14** (0.3 g, 0.9 mmol) in ether (10 ml) was added dropwise to a suspension of MeMgI in ether [prepared from MeI (2.1 g, 14.8 mmol) and activated magnesium (0.35 g, 14.4 mmol) in ether (20 ml)] at 0° under argon. The reaction mixture was allowed to attain room temperature and stirred for 12 h. It was then quenched by addition of saturated NH₄Cl solution. The organic layer was separated and the aqueous layer was extracted with ether (2×10 ml). The combined organic extracts was washed with brine, dried and concentrated. Chromatography of the residue afforded the cyclopentane derivative **18** (0.19 g, 70%) as a colourless viscous liquid: ¹H nmr δ 0.07 (6H, s), 0.88 (3H, s), 0.89 (3H, s), 0.90 (9H, s), 1.12 (3H, s), 1.58 (3H, dt, *J* 6.6 Hz and 1.5 Hz), 1.79–1.87 (1H, m), 2.06–2.30 (1H, m), 2.31–2.52 (1H, m), 3.20 (1H, bs), 3.65 (2H, dq, *J* 9 Hz and 3 Hz), 5.52–5.54 (1H, m); ¹³C nmr δ –5.41 (CH₃), 14.20 (CH₃), 17.24 (CH₃), 18.48, 22.83 (CH₃), 26.03 (CH₃), 28.19 (CH₂), 46.33, 47.39 (CH), 64.52 (OCH₂), 81.01, 115.53 (CH), 148.43.

Synthesis of the diol 19: A mixture of the silyl ether **18** (0.15 g, 0.5 mmol) and tetrabutylammonium fluoride (0.4 g, 1.5 mmol) in THF (2 ml) was stirred under nitrogen for 12 h. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was dissolved in dichloromethane. The organic layer was washed with brine, dried and concentrated. Chromatography of the residue using ether-petroleum (1 : 9) as eluent afforded the diol **19** (0.06 g, 67%) as a solid, m.p. 57–58°: (Found: C, 71.18; H, 10.76. C₁₁H₂₀O₂ calcd. for: C, 71.68; H, 10.95%); ¹H nmr δ 0.89 (3H, s), 0.90 (3H, s), 1.9 (3H, s), 1.60 (3H, d, *J* 6.6 Hz), 1.87–1.91 (1H, m), 2.25–2.27 (1H, m), 2.24–2.52 (1H, m), 2.65 (1H, bs), 3.61–3.73 (2H, m), 5.51–5.58 (1H, m); ¹³C nmr δ 14.08 (CH₃), 17.05 (CH₃), 22.03 (CH₃), 25.63 (CH₃), 28.24 (CH₂), 46.15, 47.40 (CH), 63.63 (OCH₂), 81.53, 116.13 (CH), 148.01.

2,2-Dimethyl-3-tert-butyl dimethylsilyloxymethyl-5-methoxymethylenecyclopentanone (**21**): To a magnetically stirred solution of diisopropylamine (0.07 g, 0.66 mmol) in THF (2 ml) cooled to –65° under argon, was added dropwise nBuLi (0.45 ml, 0.68 mmol, 1.5 *M* in hexane). The reaction mixture was warmed to 0° and again cooled to –65°. A solution of the ketone **14** (0.15 g, 0.45 mmol) in THF (3 ml) was then added dropwise. The reaction mixture was allowed to warm to room temperature and red gelatinous mass formed was stirred for 3 h. The reaction mixture was cooled to 0°

and quenched with saturated NH_4Cl solution. It was extracted with ether (2×10 ml). The combined organic extracts was washed with brine, dried and concentrated. Chromatographic purification of the residue using ether-petroleum (1 : 19) as eluent afforded the enone **21** (0.08 g, 60%) as a colourless thick liquid : ^1H nmr δ -0.01 (6H, s), 0.84 (9H, s), 0.87 (3H, s), 1.07 (3H, s), 1.88-1.98 (1H, m), 2.07-2.16 (1H, m), 2.56-2.65 (1H, m), 3.61 (2H, dq, J 6 Hz and 12 Hz), 3.80 (3H, s), 7.13-7.15 (1H, m); ^{13}C nmr δ -5.15 (CH_3), 18.57, 18.88 (CH_3), 24.63 (CH_3), 25.69 (CH_2), 26.22 (CH_3), 47.0 (CH), 48.49, 61.95 (OCH_3), 64.1 (OCH_2), 114.7, 154.94 (CH), 211.85 (CO).

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